

Collaborations and innovative approach of initiative Non-Communicable Disease Week program at Colombo Regional Director of Health Services (RDHS) area, Sri Lanka

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Background

- Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) pose a **major public health burden** in Sri Lanka.
- NCDs account for about **83% of annual deaths** in the country.

Methods used for evaluation

The number of stakeholders involved in the NCD week and the qualitative analysis of the level of collaboration

List of few Outreach events conducted

- Padukka Weekly Fair
- Makumbura Multimodal Transport Center
- Kottawa Bus Stand
- Meegoda Weekly Fair
- KIU University
- Nawagamawa Devalaya (Temple)
- Kaduwela Divisional Secretariat
- State Engineering Corporation of Sri Lanka
- National Medicines Regulatory Authority
- Battaramulla Divisional Secretariat
- Oruwala Temple
- Kahatuduwa Market
- Hanwella Bus Stop
- Nawagamawa Star Packaging

Fig-1

Fig 2

Fig 3- mobile medical unit

Description of the initiative

- A week-long NCD screening and awareness program was implemented aimed to **screen 5,000** at-risk individuals, providing health education, and encouraging timely medical follow-up and lifestyle modification.
- **21 Outreach programs** (fig-1,2) were conducted through **the integration of services** across hospitals, Primary Medical Care Units (PMcus), Medical Officer of Health (MOH) offices, and community-based health platforms contributions **without disrupting their routine services**. All 36 Healthy Lifestyle Centres (HLCs) operated through existing service delivery channels.
- **Private sector partners** assisted with logistics. A **mobile medical unit** (Fig- 3), provided by a private sector, facilitated outreach at outdoor locations. Community-based organizations helped in **dissemination of the messages** to the public on the NCD week and **preparation of the venues for screening**.

Challenges , Innovative solutions & Lessons Learnt

- **Key challenges** such as lack of resources, limited health care staff and transport logistics revealed the need for better operational planning.
- Innovative solutions like **mobile medical units** and **simplified health records** (Fig- 4) enabled service continuity amid resource shortages.
- **Daily meetings and daily data collection** enabled real-time identification of operational challenges and on-the-ground solutions.
- Additionally, **political sensitivities** and permissions from venues affecting program execution reinforced the need for early risk assessment and **official clearances**.
- Future programs should prioritize **data governance, stakeholder coordination, and flexible contingency planning**.

Personal Medical Record	
01. Personal Details	
Serial No: _____	Date: _____
Name: _____	
NIC No: _____	Male / Female: _____
Age: _____	Date of Birth: _____
Address: _____	
Contact No (Mobile): _____	
02. Anthropometric measurements	
Weight (kg): _____	Height (cm): _____
BMI (kg/m ²): _____	Waist Circumference (cm): _____
03. Biochemical Investigations	
Random Glucose Level (mg/dl)	_____
Fasting Glucose Level (mg/dl)	_____
Serum Cholesterol Level (mg/dl)	_____
04. Visual Acuity	
Right Eye	Left Eye
6/	6/
Notes/Referrals: _____	
5. Past medical/surgical/allergic history	

6. Family history	
Diabetes	Cancer
Hypertension	Ischemic Heart diseases
Stroke	Asthma and COPD
Kidney disease	Other
07. Behavior risk factors	
Physical Activity Levels	Sedentary: _____
	Moderate Intensity: _____
	Vigorous Intensity: _____
Tobacco Smoking	Current Smoker: _____
	Quit (Less than 1 year before): _____
Betel chewing with tobacco or areca nut	Current User: _____
	Quit (Less than 1 year before): _____
Other tobacco or areca nut products use	Current User: _____
	Quit (Less than 1 year before): _____
Alcohol Consumption	Current User: _____
	Quit (Less than 1 year before): _____
08. Risk assessment	
Blood pressure (mmHg)	_____
Risk Percentage for Cardiovascular Diseases (Non-Laboratory based Risk Factors chart)	<10% _____
	10% - <20% _____
	20% - <30% _____

Figure 04- Simplified Personal Medical Record

Conclusions

The NCD Week successfully promoted early NCD risk detection and community awareness. **Over 3500 Patients screened** through outreach events alone with actual numbers including HLCs likely higher.

This initiative highlighted the importance of **early planning**, strong intersectoral **collaboration**, and **adaptability** in implementing large-scale health programs